

Cropland abandonment and Maintenance combination: Lessons from Five Millennia of Chinese Farming for Global Farmland Management

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The development of Chinese agriculture over five millennia has been driven by the evolving relationship between humans and the land, alongside innovations in farming techniques, which have collectively propelled the transformation of cultivation systems. From the following practices of primitive agriculture to the introduction of crop rotation and fallow systems in the Bronze Age, the evolution of Chinese farming methods has significantly boosted grain yields and diversified crop cultivation (Yang et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2020). This process exemplifies the localization and adaptation of agricultural technologies within China's unique environmental context.

This paper analyses the implications of these historical transformations for global abandoned land management, highlighting how the development of Chinese farming systems has adapted to local climates and environments, thereby enhancing sustainable land use. To address the issue of inadequate abandoned land maintenance, it is proposed that traditional agricultural wisdom be integrated with modern technology, developing strategies that combine abandonment with land maintenance. Specific measures include enhancing soil organic matter, reducing pest infestations, and increasing biodiversity. Additionally, data analytics and technological tools are advocated to monitor the ecological recovery of abandoned lands, aiming to establish a comprehensive management model tailored to local environmental and economic conditions.

Reference:

1. Yang et al., West Forum, 2018. DOI: 10.3969/j.issn.1674-8131.2018.02.001.
2. Jiang et al., Journal of Shenyang Agricultural University (Social Sciences Edition), 2020. DOI: 10.3969/j.issn.1008-9713.2020.03.014